

APPLICATION OF BODY FORCE CONCEPT IN AEROACOUSTICS

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ABSTRACT

This paper is to present the application of body force concept in the immersed boundary (IB) method to aeroacoustics problems. Five kinds of body force models are given to model wall boundary conditions in a high-order in-house solver for the computational aeroacoustics. The body force models are evaluated by simulating several flow-induced sound problems including viscous flows around a stationary/ vibrating circular cylinder by solving compressible Navier-Stokes equations and gust-cascade interaction noise by solving nonlinear Euler equations. Free of empirical parameters and by exerting suitable construction manners, the influence matrix method is demonstrated most suitable to simulate both the viscous and inviscid flow-induced sound problems. It is then used to study the influence of the inclined angle between an incident gust and a cascade and the slight vibration of the cascade on radiated sound fields for gust-cascade interactions. The inclined angle of the cascade is demonstrated to have a remarkable influence on the upstream and downstream sound pressure distributions. By contrast, the slight vibration is demonstrated to only have a small influence on the radiated sound when the inter-blade-phase-angle of vibrating plates is zero.

INTRODUCTION

The computational fluid dynamics (CFD) and computational aeroacoustics (CAA) makes it possible to predict the sound generated by complex geometries and even moving boundaries such as rotor-stator interaction. However, for the popular finite difference methods (FDM), directly simulating flow-induced sound from moving boundaries like vibrating cascade is still challenging [1].

Difficult to reach optimal dispersion and dissipation relationships for high-order methods such as dispersion-relation-preserving (DRP) [2] on body-fitted types of grid, Kurbatskii and Tam [3] combined the high-order CAA schemes with Cartesian method by utilizing the backward difference stencils near wall boundaries. But numerical

instability and complex position judgement near wall boundaries limit further application to practical aeroacoustics problems such as rotor-stator interaction noise. In our previous work [4], the “2H2U” optimal criteria are summarized for simulating flow-induced sound from moving boundaries via high-order CFD/CAA. It is conceivable that the adoption of unified numerical schemes in the whole computational grid may highly improve the suitability of high-order methods for practical aeroacoustics problems. Proposed by Peskin [5], IB method is the best one to satisfy the criteria. The introduction of body force model switches wall boundary conditions (BCs) to the body force terms of momentum equations, thus governing equations can be solved on the Cartesian grid. In the original IB method, the solid domain is treated as an extension of the fluid domain. In incompressible flow simulations, there are three kinds of modelling manners for the body force: feedback [6], discretized [7] and penalization forcing methods [8]. However, the relationship and features are still not very clear. All these body force models are initially designed for low-order incompressible CFD solver. In the work of Vasilyev [8] and Sun [9] in acoustic scattering simulations over the past decade, it exhibits a promising prospect for the body force concept to be used in high-order CFD/CAA methods. Besides that, Cao and Tucker [10] applied the discretized forcing method to the performance prediction of NASA rotor 67 combined with the viscous loss model [11]. The prediction accuracy is encouraging even if the boundary layer is not resolved. Generally, it may be combined with the high-order CAA solver without resolving the boundary layer to predict the propeller noise dominated by steady sources at moderate speeds. Therefore, suitable body force models are quite critical.

In our previous work [4,12], we proved that the influence matrix method (IMM), one kind of discretized forcing method, can be well combined with the high-order CAA solver to give the exact form of body force in the prediction-correction scheme. In this paper, the body force concept is re-visited. Five body force models in Fig. 1 are

derived and evaluated by simulating the viscous flow around a stationary/vibrating circular cylinder. Whereafter, a second computational aeroacoustics (CAA) benchmark problem [13] is used to validate the “optimal” body force model by solving the nonlinear Euler equations. To take into consideration the influence of the inclined angle and the slight vibration of a cascade, the radiated sound fields from a gust interacting with stationary/vibrating flat plate cascade interaction are further simulated.

Fig. 1. Body Force Models in IB Methods.

NOMENCLATURE

\mathbf{V}	Flow velocity
\mathbf{f}	Body force density
\mathbf{F}	Boundary force density
$\mathbf{F}_{loading}$	Resultant force acted on the body
\mathbf{x}	Cartesian grid coordinate
\mathbf{X}	Boundary point coordinate
\mathbf{A}	Influence matrix
$\alpha, \beta, \gamma, \eta$	Empirical parameters of the body force models
δ_d	Regularized Dirac Delta function
$\phi(x)$	One-dimensional template function
$C_{L(rms)}$	Root-Mean-Square of lift coefficient
$\overline{C_d}$	Average drag coefficient
St	Strouhal number
u_{Gust}	X-direction gust velocity
v_{Gust}	Y-direction gust velocity
CFL	Courant- Friedrichs- Lewy
$\overline{\mathbf{V}}$	Mean velocity
Ma_∞	Inflow Mach number
AOA	Angle of Attack
$IBPA$	Inter-blade-phase-angle
ω	Gust angular frequency
ω_α	Pitching angular frequency of the cascade
α_m	Pitching vibration amplitude
α_0	Average pitching angle

METHODOLOGIES

The flow-induced sound problem can be well described by 3-D compressible N-S equations. In this paper, the in-house CFD/CAA solver illustrated in Fig. 2 is adopted. The code is written by FORTRAN-90 and parallelized by the Message-Passing Interface (MPI). The governing equations are discretized by FDM on fixed Cartesian grid due to the adoption of the IB method. And uniform grid is used near wall boundaries. Thus, the optimal dispersion relationship can be kept when the 7-points central DRP scheme is utilized. To achieve the non-

reflecting boundary conditions (NRBCs) in the far field, the nonlinear perfectly matched layer (PML) is used in the code. Besides that, it can be switched to periodic boundary conditions when simulating rotor-stator interaction problems. In particular, the high-stencils selective filtering is utilized to suppress the potential grid-to-grid oscillations. In this paper, the 9-points central filter is used in the whole computational domain including wall boundaries. The solver has been well verified in our previous work including linear acoustic scattering simulation [12] and direct numerical simulation (DNS) for the sound generated by a stationary/vibrating cylinder [4]. The computational efficiency is proved remarkably high.

Fig. 2. CFD/CAA Parallel Solver [4,12].

In the in-house solver, the IB method is the core module, and now it will be extended with different body force models in this paper. In our previous work [4], an excellent model-IMM belonging to BF2-1 in Fig. 1 is developed for compressible N-S equations. And to evaluate the body force models BF1-1, BF1-2, BF2-1, BF2-2 and BF3 in Fig. 1, the body force models are derived to satisfy no-slip wall BCs. For brevity, the momentum equations are denoted as

$$\partial(\rho\mathbf{V})/\partial t = \mathbf{RHS} + \mathbf{f}, \quad (1)$$

where the \mathbf{RHS} is the summation of advection, diffusion and pressure gradient terms. The quantities have been nondimensionalized by the body characteristic length D , the inflow sound speed c_∞ , the inflow static density ρ_∞ , the incoming flow viscosity μ_∞ .

(a) Body-fitted Methods; (b) IB Methods.

Fig. 3. Control Volume and the Principles of Different Methods to Satisfy Wall Boundary Conditions (Ω_1 : solid domain or extended fluid domain; Ω_2 : fluid domain).

In the classical body-fitted type of methods in Fig. 3(a), wall boundary conditions are directly imposed by revising the fundamental physical quantities- velocity \mathbf{V} , density ρ and temperature T near wall boundaries. In the original IB method in Fig. 3(b), the body force \mathbf{f} is used to indirectly substitute the wall effect, that is, no-slip

effect or no-penetration effect. And the solid domain is treated as an extension of the fluid domain. The wall boundaries in Fig. 3(a) are treated as immersed boundary by introducing the Lagrangian boundary force and Eulerian body force. Thus the calculation of loading on the body is revised as

$$\mathbf{F}_{loading} = \sum_{\Omega_1+\Omega_2} \mathbf{f} - \iiint_{\Omega_1} [\partial(\rho\mathbf{V})/\partial t] d\mathbf{x}, \quad (2)$$

$\mathbf{F}_{loading}$ is usually calculated by adding the pressure force and viscous force. $\sum_{\Omega_1+\Omega_2} \mathbf{f}$ represents the summation of the body force exerted on the Cartesian grid. The last term in Eq. (2) represents the momentum variation in the extended fluid domain Ω_1 . In practical calculations for a stationary body, once the wall boundary velocity approaches zero, the last term in Eq. (2) can be neglected. And for a vibrating rigid body, the last term in Eq. (2) is approximately equal to product of the fluid mass in Ω_1 and the accelerated velocity of the vibrating body. Once the wall boundary velocity approaches zero, the fluid mass in Ω_1 is almost kept a constant and only needs once calculation in the beginning. Therefore, the body force model is of vital importance for the satisfaction of wall boundary conditions in the IB methods. There are five body force modeling ways in Fig. 1 according to the summary of previous incompressible flow simulations. The body force forms for compressible N-S equations are given in the following.

(1) BF1-1: integral forcing;

$$\mathbf{F} = \alpha \int_0^t [\rho\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w} - \rho\mathbf{V}_w] dt + \beta [\rho\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w} - \rho\mathbf{V}_w], \quad (3)$$

(2) BF1-2: differential forcing;

$$\mathbf{F} = \gamma [\rho\mathbf{V}_w - \rho\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w}] / \Delta t, \quad (4)$$

(3) BF2-1: prediction-correction forcing [4,14];

$$(\rho\mathbf{V}_w - \rho\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w})^T / \Delta t = \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{F}^T, \quad (5)$$

(4) BF2-2: non-prediction-correction forcing;

$$\mathbf{F} = -\mathbf{RHS}^n + [\rho\mathbf{V}_w - \rho\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w}^n] / \Delta t, \quad (6)$$

(5) BF3: penalization forcing.

$$\mathbf{f} = \chi(\rho\mathbf{V}_w - \rho\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w}) / \eta, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{k=1}^M \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}_k) \delta_d(\mathbf{x} - \mathbf{X}_k) \Delta S_k, \quad (8)$$

$$\sum_{\Omega_1+\Omega_2} \mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_{\Gamma} \mathbf{F}(\mathbf{X}), \quad (9)$$

$$\delta_d(\mathbf{r}) = \frac{1}{d_x d_y} \phi\left(\frac{r_x}{d_x}\right) \phi\left(\frac{r_y}{d_y}\right), \quad (10)$$

$$\chi = \begin{cases} 1, & \mathbf{x} \in \Omega_1, \\ 0, & \mathbf{x} \notin \Omega_1, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where w denotes the wall boundary point. $f \rightarrow w$ denotes the fluid points coinciding with wall boundary points. And χ in Eq. (11) is the mask function. d_x and d_y are the mesh sizes in the two directions, r_x and r_y are the distances of the immersed boundary point from the Cartesian grid point in two directions, $\delta_d(\mathbf{r})$ function is

highly compact-support. n denotes the last time step. M is the number of boundary points. Eq. (8) is used to distribute the boundary force density \mathbf{F} in Eqs. (3-6) to the Cartesian grid. Particularly, the optimized Delta function δ_d in [15] is used for the high-order solver. It is verified that the numerical oscillations of body force can be alleviated [4]. Remarkably, the body force models BF1-1, 1-2 and 2-2 have some slight differences from the original forms [6,7] due to the introduction of the boundary force density. The reason why we adopt the revised body force models in BF1-1, 1-2 and 2-2 in this paper is mainly because of the convenient access of the final loading $\mathbf{F}_{loading}$ by introducing the boundary force model obeying the relationship in Eqs. (8) and (9).

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The no-slip wall BCs error is defined as

$$L_2 = \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^M (\mathbf{V}_{f \rightarrow w} - \mathbf{V}_w)^2 / M}, \quad (12)$$

In addition, the time-averaged body force distributions for different body force model are calculated. The numerical cases are divided into two types: simulating viscous flow and sound around a circular cylinder and simulating the inviscid flow and radiated sound field from a gust/cascade interaction. The first type of case has been widely used in the previous validation for IB methods validation. So there are abundant numerical data to be accessible. The second type of case is the simplest benchmark problem for studying the fundamental problems in turbomachines. Both analytical and numerical methods have been developed for this kind of case. When the AOA of a cascade changes, both the mean loading and the inclined angle between the incident gust and the cascade change, too. And the mean loading of the cascade has been demonstrated to have a significant influence on the radiated sound according to the studies in Ref. [16]. Therefore, in the present paper, the influence of the inclined angle is mainly studied, which means that the induced body force by background flow will not be included into the final body force terms. The influence of slight vibration of cascade on radiated sound almost has no corresponding studies yet. Only some studies have been conducted around the radiated noise from the gust/vibrating airfoil interaction in non-uniform flow [17]. So much attention is paid to the influence of slight vibration of the cascade on radiated sound fields in the final part.

A. 2-D Cylinder Streaming

To evaluate the body force models BF1-1, 1-2, 2-1, 2-2 and BF3 used in the high-order CAA solver, two kinds of 2-D cylinder streaming cases are taken into consideration: (1) $Re_\infty = 40,150$, $Ma_\infty = 0.2$, stationary; (2) $Re_\infty = 150$, $Ma_\infty = 0.2$, transverse vibration with the motion equation $y = 0.2 \sin(0.03\pi \cdot t)$. The first kind of cases can test the response of different body force models to the steady/unsteady flows. The second kind of case is usually difficult to be directly simulated by utilizing high-order CAA method. The adoption of the body force concept

makes it feasible to utilize the current solver to simulate the flow field and the radiated sound. And the first kind of cases has been studied in our previous work [4] by utilizing the IMM in BF2-1. Good agreement is obtained with other published data. In this part, the computational domain, the mesh, the filtering intensity and the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy (CFL) number are all kept same for all the cases and are listed in Tab. 1. Each simulation is started with an initial flow field calculated with a low Reynolds number $Re_\infty = 20$. The no-slip wall BCs error L_2 in Eq. (12) is viewed as a critical criterion to evaluate the five body force models. The convergence results for the wall BCs error L_2 are shown in Fig. 4. And the calculated lift C_L , drag coefficients C_d and Strohaul number (St) by utilizing different body force models are shown in Tab. 2.

$$\alpha = -10, \beta = 0.0, \gamma = 1.0, \eta = 0.005, \quad (13)$$

In this part, because a large CFL number is adopted for all the cases, suitable empirical parameters are quite important for the BF1-1, 1-2 and BF3 to maintain the numerical stability. From our numerical experiments, we found that the above values in Eq. (13) are suitable for the BF1-1, 1-2 and BF3. In Eq. (13), $\beta = 0.0$ means that the amplitude of error L_2 will not decay over time, but kept a constant. Therefore, the condition that the feedback frequency must exceed to the concerned unsteady fluctuation frequency becomes essential for unsteady flow simulations. However, it is usually conflictive with numerical stability requirements. $\gamma = 1.0$ means that the calculated body force via the BF1-1 is approximately equal to that via the BF2-2 except for the RHS term in Eq. (6). And the value, $\eta = 0.005$, only causes a small error from Ref. [8].

Tab. 1. Computational Parameters.

Computational Domain	M	CFL	dx	Filtering Intensity
$[-6, 14] \times [-7, 7]$	300	0.5	0.01	0.08

Fig. 4. Convergence for the Wall BCs Error L_2 .

Fig. 5. the Instantaneous Lift and Drag Coefficients with changing time. ($Re_\infty = 40$, Stationary)

Fig. 6. the Instantaneous Lift and Drag Coefficients with changing time. ($Re_\infty = 150$, Stationary)

Fig. 7. The Instantaneous Lift and Drag Coefficients. ($Re_\infty = 150$, Vibrating)

From the calculated convergence curves of the wall BCs error L_2 in Fig. 4, it can be seen that, in consideration of the convergent speed for the satisfaction of wall BCs, $BF1-1 = BF2-1 > BF1-2 = BF2-2 > BF3$. However, numerical oscillation occurs in the initial phase for the BF1-1, especially for the vibrating cylinder case, which may limit the further application of the model to complex unsteady flow problems. An effective remedial measure is to adopt a more smooth flow field to initialize the flow field, thus to weaken the numerical oscillation. In fact, a good initial flow field is always good for all the body force models. Therefore, the BF2-1 has the best convergence quality than other body force models.

Tab. 2. Comparison between Different BFMs. (p'_{rms} is taken at $r = 5$ and $\theta = 90^\circ$)

Case	BFM	$C_{L(rms)}$	$\overline{C_d}$	St	$p'_{rms} (\times 10^3)$
Case (1) Re=40, Stationary	BF1-1	-	1.57	-	-
	BF1-2	-	1.60	-	-
	BF2-1	-	1.60	-	-
	BF2-2	-	1.55	-	-
	BF3	-	1.48-1.63	-	-
Russell et al. (2003) [18]					
Case (1) Re=150, Stationary	BF1-1	0.37	1.37	0.187	3.87
	BF1-2	0.32	1.45	0.187	3.40
	BF2-1	0.37	1.37	0.187	3.87
	BF2-2	0.33	1.45	0.187	3.41
	BF3	0.36	1.33	0.187	3.78
Inoue et al. (2002) [19]					
		0.37	1.32	0.183	-

	BF1-1	0.075	1.32	0.150	1.00
Case (2)	BF1-2	0.093	1.42	0.150	0.80
Re=150,	BF2-1	0.075	1.32	0.150	1.01
Vibrating	BF2-2	0.093	1.42	0.150	0.79
	BF3	0.068	1.29	0.150	1.06
Komatsu et al. (2016) [20]		0.065	1.28	0.150	-

Considering the computational efficiency including interpolation operations, point judgement and matrix operations, the ranking becomes: BF1-1 = BF1-2 > BF3 > BF2-2 > BF2-1. The BF1-1, BF1-2 and BF3 only need local velocity in the present time step when constructing their body forces. But BF3 needs solving the mask function in Eq. (11) to judge point positions. The BF2-2 needs the local velocity in the present time step and the spatial derivatives, which makes it complicated to be completed in a parallel code. The BF2-1 needs the local velocities in two time steps and solving linear equations. In Ref. [4], the coefficient matrix is deeply analyzed, thus a fast parallel algorithm (parallel preconditioned conjugate gradient method, PPCGM) with a low storage is developed to highly lower computation and memory requirements.

Tab. 3. Evaluation for the Five Body Force Models Applied to the High-order CAA Methods. (☆☆☆: Excellent, ☆☆: Good, ☆: Weak; √: Yes, ×: No).

BFM	BF1-1	BF1-2	BF2-1	BF2-2	BF3
Wall BCs Satisfaction	☆☆☆	☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆	☆
Numerical Stability	☆	☆☆	☆☆☆	☆☆	☆☆☆
Computational Efficiency	☆☆☆	☆☆☆	☆	☆	☆☆
Matrix Operation	×	×	√	×	×
Only Local Variables	√	√	√	×	√
Inner Point Distinction	×	×	×	×	√
Empirical Parameters	√	√	×	×	√

In addition, the BF3 have been proved an excellent IB method to be combined with high-order CAA schemes in Ref. [8]. In our present numerical experiments, the wall BCs via the BF3 are not satisfied so well. But the velocity of the interior points near the wall boundaries rapidly declines to a small quantity $O(10^{-5} \sim -3)$ for all the above cases. So for numerical stability, the BF3 is actually an excellent body force model. According to the numerical analysis above, we can come to a conclusion about the advantages and disadvantages of the above body force models when combined with the high-order CAA schemes as shown in Tab. 3.

Fig. 8. Body Force Distributions along the Immersed Boundaries. ($Re_\infty = 40$, Stationary)

Fig. 9. Body Force Distributions along the Immersed Boundaries. ($Re_\infty = 150$, Stationary)

Fig. 10. Body Force Distributions along the Immersed Boundaries. ($Re_\infty = 150$, Vibrating)

Fig. 11. Contours of Body Force f_x and f_y Distributions for the BF3. (A: x-direction; B: y-direction, $Re_\infty = 150$, Stationary)

It can be seen that the BF2-1 has great superiority over other models in overall performance except for the computational efficiency from Tab. 3. But in our previous work, we proved that the computational efficiency can be improved greatly if our developed fast algorithm and storage scheme for sparse matrixes in Ref. [4] are adopted. So in the next part about the flow-induced sound simulation for the stationary/vibrating flat plate cascade, the BF2-1 is adopted for all the cases. In addition, the body force distributions along the immersed boundaries for different BFMs are plotted in Figs. 8~11. Due to the imposition of body force in the interior of the extended fluid domain in BF3, there have obvious force distribution in the extended fluid domain in Fig. 11.

B. 2-D Flat Plate Cascade Flow

The flat plate cascade flow in Fig. 5 is simple, so it is usually used to investigate the rotor-stator interaction noise and vibration phenomena in turbomachines due to the possible access to linear theories and analytical methods under some circumstances [13]. However, the linear

theories and analytical methods usually cannot take into consideration the following factors: swirling flow, geometry, flow-sound interaction, cascade vibration and cascade with mean loading. Due to the adoption of the body force model, the present CAA solver can take into consideration all the above factors theoretically. In the present work, the nonlinear Euler equations are solved to investigate the gust-cascade interaction problems in combination with the inviscid body force model. Then the influence of the inclined angle and the slight vibration of cascade on the scattering process of the incident disturbances will be investigated.

Fig. 12. 2-D Flat Plate Cascade Model (c : chord length; g : cascade gap; a : position of axis O).

B-1: BENCHMARK CASES

Firstly, sound generated by the interaction of a 2D gust with a vibrating cascade illustrated in Fig. 12 is simulated. The problem is from the category 3 of the Second CAA Workshop. When a cascade of flat plates works in zero AOA and high-Reynold number, the boundary layer is thin and the interaction of zero-thickness flat plate with the concerned incident gust is weak. Therefore, the nonlinear Euler equations are the most suitable and cheapest way to describe the interaction process. In the following, we compare our results with the linearized inviscid results for the stationary flat plate cascade case. In this case, the inflow Mach number, Ma_∞ , is 0.5. The gap-to-chord, g/c , is 1.0. The computational domain is $[-2.7, 2.7] \times [-2, 2]$. The inflow and outflow are at $x = -2.7$ and $x = 2.7$, respectively. The upstream and downstream are periodic boundaries, and the inflow and outflow boundaries are NRBCs, which are implemented by utilizing the nonlinear PML equations with gust-related sources in ANNEX A. There are four flat plates in the computational domain. The axis O of the flat plates is at $x = 0$. In this paper, the axis O is at the middle of the cascade, and the original point, $(0, 0)$, is at the centre of the computational domain.

The vortical gust carried by the mean flow has x and y velocity components given by

$$\begin{cases} u'_{Gust} = -(v_G k_y / k_x) \cos(k_x x + k_y y - \omega t) \\ v'_{Gust} = v_G \cos(k_x x + k_y y - \omega t) \end{cases}, \quad (13)$$

where $k_x = k_y = 5\pi/2$ and $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$ for two cases.

To initialize the flow field, the cascade is removed from the computational domain firstly. The gust is added in the inflow PML domain as source terms. When the gust travels across the whole computational domain, the normal body force of the flat plates is applied into the flow field.

To avoid the nonlinear effect in the simulation, $v_G = 0.005$ is used. To import the gust into the PML, the pseudo velocity of the mean flow in the PML domain is revised from $\bar{V} = (Ma_\infty, 0)$ to $\bar{V} = (Ma_\infty + u'_{Gust}, v'_{Gust})$. Thus good non-reflecting quality can be obtained. The large-scale gust can allow a sparse mesh to figure out the gust propagation and the scattered sound waves. In the first case with no consideration of the cascade, the discretized point numbers along the flat plate are $M = 100$ corresponding to the grid size, $\Delta x = 0.01$. And an uniform grid is used both in the x and y directions. A large CFL number, $CFL = 0.8$, is adopted. The plots of gust propagation and the fluctuating pressure at point $(-2.5, 0.0)$ are shown in Fig. 13. It can be seen that the periodic vertical gust is successfully imported into the computational domain without any damping and with only a small reflecting pressure wave motivated.

Fig. 13. The x-direction Gust Velocity Contours (A) and the Fluctuating Pressure (B) at point $(-2.5, 0.0)$ (No Cascade).

In the gust-cascade interaction case, two different CFL numbers, $CFL = 0.6, 0.4$, and two sets of grid sizes, $\Delta x = 0.01, 0.005$, are adopted to check the convergence of the acoustic field. The pressure difference on the flat plate with $y = -0.5$ (Plate 2) and the root mean squares of acoustic pressure, p'_{rms} , on the line $x = -2.5$ and $x = 2.5$ are calculated. The calculated results by utilizing the IB method are compared with the exact results calculated by the LINSUB and the numerical results [22]. The acoustic pressure on the lines $x = -2.5$ and $x = 2.5$ are illustrated in Figs. 14 and 15.

Fig. 14. Root-Mean-Square (RMS) Pressure at Upstream Boundary $x = -2.5$ and Downstream Boundary $x = 2.5$ for Different CFL Numbers ($\Delta x = 0.01, \omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

Fig. 15. Root-Mean-Square (RMS) Pressure at Upstream Boundary $x = -2.5$ and Downstream Boundary $x = 2.5$ for Different Grid Sizes ($CFL = 0.4$, $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

Figure 14 shows that, with decreasing the CFL number, the calculated acoustic pressure distributions between two flat plates have a good convergence. However, the calculated acoustic pressure distributions don't perfectly coincide with the exact solution. It is because that the leading and trailing edges singularity is actually not satisfied well in most FDMs due to the insufficient grid points near the leading and trailing edges where the unsteady Kutta conditions are usually applied explicitly in the analytical methods. In Fig. 15, it can be seen that the numerical solution is closer to the exact solution with refining the grid. In addition, the pressure difference on the flat plate surface is calculated and plotted in Fig. 16. The numerical probes are located $2\Delta x$ as far as the blade surface along the normal direction. Fig. 16 shows that there is a correspondence between the real and imaginary parts of the exact solution and the imaginary pressure and real parts of the present results for the acoustic pressure. The reason is that the initial phase in the present simulation is different from that of the exact solution due to the different position of the flat plate cascade. In the problem of the second CAA workshop, the lowest flat plate is located on the lower boundary, while the lowest flat plate in Fig. 12 is located $0.5c$ far from the boundary.

Fig. 16. Pressure Difference $\Delta p'$ on the Flat Plate Surface ($CFL = 0.6$, $\Delta x = 0.005$, $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

Fig. 17. Instantaneous Fluctuating Pressure contour at $t = 100$ ($CFL = 0.6$, $\Delta x = 0.01$, $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

Particularly, the amplitude of the acoustic pressure difference calculated in the present simulation in the leading edge is lower than that in the exact solution. It makes the difference of the prediction of the acoustic pressure in Figs. 14 and 15. The instantaneous pressure field in Fig. 17 is also plotted. Pressure waves with strong intensity are observed both near the leading edge and near the trailing edge.

From the results of the above gust/zero-loading and stationary flat plate cascade interaction case, our developed in-house code for the nonlinear Euler equations are demonstrated a powerful tool to investigate the sound generation, scattering and propagation problems owing to the convenient Cartesian grid system and good body force model-IMM. Generally, a flow-induced sound problem for a lifting surface is dominated by the lift dipole other than the drag dipole if we neglect the turbulent sound sources. For the design point in turbomachines, the lift acted on blades can be usually described by the inviscid nonlinear Euler equations or even small perturbation equations such as lifting surface theory [21]. Utilizing the normal body force to model the no-penetration wall boundary condition for the Euler equations is an economic way and has a sufficiently accuracy for the sound field prediction from the above validation. In the following, the present in-house solver and the developed inviscid body force model-IMM are adopted to investigate the influence of the inclined angle and the slight vibration of the flat plate cascade on the radiated sound field. The computational domain is kept same as the above. A dense grid size, $\Delta x = 0.005$, is adopted to guarantee a sophisticated capture of the sound source intensity in the leading edge for all the cases below. And a large CFL number, $CFL = 0.6$, is adopted.

B-2: CASCADE FLOW WITH NON-ZERO AOAs

When the cascade works in non-zero AOA status, both the inclined angle and mean loading of the cascade will be changed. A typical effect of the mean loading on the radiated sound fields has been investigated in Atassi's work [16]. In this part, the influence of the inclined angle between a gust and the cascade is studied. And a 2D gust interacting with a flat plate cascade in a small $AOA = 3^\circ, 6^\circ$ is investigated. Correspondingly, the inclined angles between the incident gust and the cascade are 138° and 141° . The gust wave numbers and frequency are all kept same as above. The numerical probes are still located on

the lines $x = -2.5$ and $x = 2.5$. The RMSs of acoustic pressure for different AOAs are plotted in Fig. 18.

Fig. 18. Root-Mean-Square (RMS) of Acoustic Pressure at Upstream direction $x = -2.5$ and Downstream direction $x = 2.5$ for Different AOAs ($CFL = 0.6$, $\Delta x = 0.005$, $Ma_\infty = 0.5$, $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

It can be seen that the acoustic pressure intensity on the upstream decreases with increasing the AOA of the flat plates, which means that the increased inclined angle between the incident gust and the cascade actually reduces the intensity of the forward propagating sound waves. Meantime, it has a contrary tendency for the acoustic pressure intensity on the downstream from Fig. 18. However, it also illustrates that the increased inclined angle doesn't change the position of the maximum acoustic pressure intensity along the transverse direction. The corresponding instantaneous fluctuating pressure waves are plotted in Fig. 19 for the difference AOAs. When the flat plate cascade works in $AOA = 6^\circ$ status, the forward propagating sound waves become quite weak and are almost cut-off.

The plots of the RMS of acoustic pressure on the flat plate surface for different AOAs are illustrated in Fig. 20. In the flat plate section near the trailing edge, both the real and imaginary parts of the fluctuating pressure difference for the lower and upper surface reach the largest in the $AOA = 3^\circ$ other than the $AOA = 6^\circ$.

Fig. 19. Instantaneous Fluctuating Pressure contour at $t = 100$ ($CFL = 0.6$, $\Delta x = 0.005$, $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

Fig. 20. Fluctuating Pressure Difference $\Delta p'$ on the Third Flat Plate Surface for Different AOAs ($CFL = 0.6$, $\Delta x = 0.005$, $\omega = (5\pi/2) \cdot Ma_\infty$).

B-3: CASCADE FLOW WITH SLIGHT VIBRATION

The slight vibration of the cascade can change the surface loading distributions of the flat plate significantly. However, the mean loading change is not taken into consideration in this paper. Only the influence of the slight vibration on the upwash and downwash of the incident gust is investigated. And we initially study the influence of low-frequency vibration on the radiated sound, which means that the cascade only vibrates near its natural vibration frequencies. The acoustic radiated from the gust interacting with a pitching cascade is investigated. The pitching motion equation is

$$\alpha(t) = \alpha_m \sin(\omega_\alpha t) + \alpha_0, \quad (15)$$

where α_0 represents the initial AOA. α_m represents the pitching amplitude. And ω_α is the pitching frequency. The pitching center is at the middle point for each flat plate. The gust frequency, $\omega = (5\pi/2)/Ma_\infty$, is still considered. The AOA, $\alpha_0 = 0^\circ$, and a small pitching amplitude, $\alpha_m = 1^\circ$, are considered at present. And a vibration frequency, $\omega_\alpha = 0.1\omega$, is studied. This value is a typical natural frequency for the first-order torsional vibration in turbomachinery. The vibration inter-blade-phase-angle (IBPA) between the four flat plates is kept

zero, which means that all the flat plates vibrates synchronously.

Fig. 21. Sketch of the Computational Grid and Computational Model (one point for ten).

Due to the adoption of inviscid body force model, it is no need for the grid shown in Fig. 21 to move with the pitching movement of the cascade. And the introduction of the IMM in BF2-1 confirms the smooth solution near the surface of the flat plates without motivating observable spurious waves. The calculated instantaneous pressure waves for plate 2 are plotted in Fig. 22. In spite of the symmetric vibration, the instantaneous flow field near the second flat plate at $t=0$ and $t=2T/4$ are asymmetric because the main source of the fluctuating pressure is from the incident gust. And the instantaneous contours show that the developed inviscid body force model BF2-1 can well capture the pressure wave fluctuations on the plate surface with the vibration of the cascade without motivating spurious waves. And strong-intensity sound waves are radiated from the leading and trailing edges when the inflow gust swirls and the cascade vibrates. If we subtract the instantaneous pressure in the upstream point $(-2.5, 0)$ and do the Fast Fourier Transformation (FFT) in Fig. 23. We can find that the scattered sound field from the gust-cascade interaction dominates and the vibration-related sound can be neglected compared with the whole sound pressure level (SPL). These results mean that, to some extent, the noise prediction for the fan/outlet noise may be reasonable with neglecting the radiated sound from the vibration effects when the fan/outlet oscillates in a low mode such as the first-bending and first-torsion modes.

To quantitatively evaluate the influence of slight vibration ($\sim 1^\circ$) on the radiated sound field, acoustic pressure intensities on the lines at $x=-2.5$ and $x=2.5$ are calculated in Fig. 24. The acoustic intensities for the stationary case and vibrating case have a small difference in some transverse positions. However, the averaged value and trend are almost same, which is consistent with the above analysis for the acoustic pressure spectrum in Fig. 23. In our present work, only the case with $IBPA=0^\circ$ for the vibrating cascade is considered. However, the IBPA in real annular cascade is quite complex and usually not a constant. The present case is only a preliminary attempt to validate the in-house solver combined with the body force model BF2-1 and study the influence of slight vibration on rotor-stator interaction noise. Further results will be done in the further work.

Fig. 22. Instantaneous Pressure near the plate 2 in a Vibration Period ($CFL=0.6$, $\omega_a=0.1\omega$, $T=2\pi/\omega$).

Fig. 23. Instantaneous Acoustic Pressure at Point $(-2.5, 0)$ and Its related Frequency-Amplitude Spectrum via FFT.

Fig. 24. Root-Mean-Square of Acoustic Pressure At Upstream Boundary and Downstream Boundary for the Stationary Cascade and Slightly Vibrating Cascade.

SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION

In this paper, a high-order CFD/CAA solver is introduced. Five body force models BF1-1, 1-2, 2-1, 2-2 and 3 distinguished on the basis of modelling manners are given for compressible momentum equations. Then cylinder streaming is used as the benchmark case to evaluate the body force models. It is found that all body force models can allow a large CFL number ($O(10^{-1-0})$) if the smoothed approximate Dirac Delta function is adopted,

other than the previous conclusion that the feedback forcing type of methods can only allow a quite small CFL number ($O(10^{-3\sim-2})$). Besides that, the convergence behaviours of the five body force models are quite different. The calculated results show that the BF1-2 and BF2-2 are not correct enough, compared with the BF1-1, BF2-1 and BF3, for the viscous flow problems. The final numerical experiments and analysis demonstrate that the BF2-1 is the most excellent model while the BF1-1 requires the lowest computer resources. For practical complex problems, the two body force models actually can be combined with each other for different component. For example, aimed at predicting the fan noise with nacelle, the BF2-1 can be used to model the core components- fan blades to obtain a more accurate description for the wall boundary conditions, while due to the easy implementation, the BF1-1 can be adopted to represent the nacelle wall boundaries which usually affects the sound propagation and is not the main sound source.

Finally, a 2D gust interacting with a flat plate cascade is simulated. The inviscid nonlinear Euler equations are solved. And the body force model BF2-1 is adopted. An excellent agreement is obtained with the exact solution for the benchmark problems. It is proved that the previous in-house code and the body force model BF2-1 can satisfy the unsteady Kutta condition in the leading and trailing edges well. Furthermore, the influence of the inclined angle and slight vibration of the flat plate is investigated. It is found that: (1) the present method can achieve the near-field sound source simulation and upstream and downstream sound propagation prediction conveniently; (2) the influence of the inclined angle on the upstream and downstream sound intensities is different. However, it needs further investigation for a more general law. (3) When the cascade vibrates in a low frequency, a low amplitude and zero IBPA, the vibration has a small influence on the upstream and downstream sound intensities. It is much worth expectation to investigate the influence of more vibration parameters on the sound field, because the simulation may not only be a proof for the possibility of the body force concept to be applied to complex aeroacoustics problems in turbomachinery, but also illuminate the influence of practical vibrations such as forced excitation from the adjacent blade rows and asynchronous resonance on the rotor-stator interaction noise.

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ANNEX A

NON-REFLECTING BOUNDARY CONDITIONS FOR GUST-CASCADE INTERACTION

A suitable non-reflecting boundary condition is quite important for the gust-cascade interaction problems. In this paper, the nonlinear PML NRBCs for Euler equations are adopted. However, the original forms of the PML equations cannot be directly used for the gust-cascade problems due to the imposition of the gust in the inflow position. In our present solver, we just modify the PML equations to take into consideration the instantaneous gust as source terms in the Euler equations in the PML domain. In particular, only parallel pseudo mean flow is considered at present. The 2-D Euler equations are written in the conservative form as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_2}{\partial y} = 0, \quad (\text{A.1})$$

where

$$\mathbf{U} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho \\ \rho u \\ \rho v \\ E \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}_1 = \begin{bmatrix} \rho u \\ \rho u^2 + p \\ \rho uv \\ (E + p)u \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{F}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} \rho v \\ \rho uv \\ \rho v^2 + p \\ (E + p)v \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where $E = \rho(u^2 + v^2)/2 + p/(\gamma - 1)$ is the total energy.

In the PML absorbing boundary conditions for nonlinear simulations, the unsteady conservative \mathbf{U} can be regarded as consisting of a time-independent mean state and a time-dependent fluctuation. The time-independent mean state is usually necessary to be known exactly. To absorb the out-going waves without damping the gust information, the total velocity can be decomposed into three terms as

$$\mathbf{u} = \bar{\mathbf{u}} + \mathbf{u}'_{Gust} + \mathbf{u}', \quad (\text{A.3})$$

where $\mathbf{u} = (u, v)$, $\bar{\mathbf{u}} = (u_\infty, 0)$, $\mathbf{u}'_{Gust} = (u'_{Gust}, v'_{Gust})$ and $\mathbf{u}' = (u', v')$ are considered in 2-D case. Due to the basic assumption that the pseudo mean flow is in the direction of x-axis, the velocity in the y direction is zero. Other variables are decomposed as

$$p = p_\infty + p', \quad (\text{A.4})$$

$$\rho = \rho_\infty + \rho'. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

Due to the one-dimensional mean flow assumption in the inflow PML zones and the linear gust, we can write the PML equations in Ref. [23] in combination with the Eqs. (A.3) (A.4) and (A.5) as

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{U}}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_1}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_2}{\partial y} + \mathbf{S}_0 = 0, \quad (\text{A.6})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}_1}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_1}{\partial x} + \mathbf{S}_1 = 0, \quad (\text{A.7})$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{q}_2}{\partial t} + \frac{\partial \mathbf{F}_2}{\partial y} + \mathbf{S}_2 = 0, \quad (\text{A.8})$$

where the source terms are in the form of

$$\mathbf{S}_0 = \mathbf{S}_{0(p)} + \mathbf{S}_{0(Gust)}, \quad (\text{A.9})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_1 = \mathbf{S}_{1(p)} + \mathbf{S}_{1(Gust)}, \quad (\text{A.10})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_2 = \mathbf{S}_{2(p)} + \mathbf{S}_{2(Gust)}, \quad (\text{A.11})$$

where the components are equal to

$$\mathbf{S}_{0(p)} = \sigma_x \mathbf{q}_1 + \sigma_y \mathbf{q}_2 + \beta \sigma_x [\mathbf{F}_{1(p)} - \overline{\mathbf{F}_{1(p)}}], \quad (\text{A.12})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{0(Gust)} = -\beta \sigma_x \mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)} - \partial \mathbf{u}'_{Gust} / \partial t - \partial \mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)} / \partial x - \partial \mathbf{F}'_{2(Gust)} / \partial y - (\sigma_x + \sigma_y) \mathbf{u}'_{Gust}, \quad (\text{A.13})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{1(p)} = \sigma_x \mathbf{q}_1 + \beta \sigma_x [\mathbf{F}_{1(p)} - \overline{\mathbf{F}_{1(p)}}], \quad (\text{A.14})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{1(Gust)} = -\beta \sigma_x \mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)} - \partial \mathbf{u}'_{Gust} / \partial t - \partial \mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)} / \partial x - \sigma_x \mathbf{u}'_{Gust}, \quad (\text{A.15})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{2(p)} = \sigma_y \mathbf{q}_2, \quad (\text{A.16})$$

$$\mathbf{S}_{2(Gust)} = -\partial \mathbf{F}'_{2(Gust)} / \partial y - \partial \mathbf{u}'_{Gust} / \partial t - \sigma_y \mathbf{u}'_{Gust}, \quad (\text{A.17})$$

where $[\mathbf{F}_{1(p)} - \overline{\mathbf{F}_{1(p)}}]$ represents the inflow pseudo mean flow without the gust, and $\mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)}$ and $\mathbf{F}'_{2(Gust)}$ are related to the gust. By neglecting the high-order gust terms, the terms can be written as

$$[\mathbf{F}_{1(p)} - \overline{\mathbf{F}_{1(p)}}] = \begin{bmatrix} \rho u - \rho_\infty u_\infty \\ \rho u^2 + p - (\rho_\infty u_\infty^2 + p_\infty) \\ \rho uv \\ (E + p)u - (E_\infty + p_\infty)u_\infty \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.18})$$

$$\mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)} = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_\infty \dot{u}_{Gust} \\ 2\rho_\infty u_\infty \dot{u}_{Gust} \\ \rho_\infty u_\infty \dot{v}_{Gust} \\ (E_\infty + p_\infty + \rho_\infty u_\infty^2) \dot{u}_{Gust} \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.19})$$

$$\partial \dot{\mathbf{u}}_{Gust} / \partial t = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \rho_\infty f_t \\ \rho_\infty g_t \\ \rho_\infty u_\infty f_t \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.20})$$

$$\partial \mathbf{F}'_{1(Gust)} / \partial x = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_\infty f_x \\ 2\rho_\infty u_\infty f_x \\ \rho_\infty u_\infty g_x \\ (E_\infty + p_\infty + \rho_\infty u_\infty^2) f_x \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.21})$$

$$\partial \mathbf{F}'_{2(Gust)} / \partial y = \begin{bmatrix} \rho_\infty g_y \\ \rho_\infty u_\infty g_y \\ 0 \\ (E_\infty + p_\infty) g_y \end{bmatrix}, \quad (\text{A.22})$$

where the subscripts 'p' and 'Gust' are the pseudo mean flow in the original PML equations in Ref. [23] and the gust-related sources. And ρ_∞ , u_∞ , p_∞ and E_∞ are all inflow mean variables. We give the gust in the general form of

$$\begin{cases} \dot{u}_{Gust} = f(x, y, t) \\ \dot{v}_{Gust} = g(x, y, t) \end{cases} \quad (\text{A.23})$$

Therefore, the derivatives of the gust can be obtained as

$$\begin{cases} \partial \dot{u}_{Gust} / \partial t = f_t \\ \partial \dot{u}_{Gust} / \partial x = f_x \\ \partial \dot{u}_{Gust} / \partial y = f_y \end{cases}, \quad (\text{A.24})$$

$$\begin{cases} \partial \dot{v}_{Gust} / \partial t = g_t \\ \partial \dot{v}_{Gust} / \partial x = g_x \\ \partial \dot{v}_{Gust} / \partial y = g_y \end{cases}. \quad (\text{A.25})$$

For a prescribed gust which can be usually obtained with empirical formulas or CFD results, the derivatives f_t , f_x , f_y , g_t , g_x and g_y can be calculated in advance. Remarkably, the introduced gust can be treated as the source terms in the form of Eq. (A.13), (A.15) and (A.17) in the PML equations. It is convenient to apply the revised PML equations related to the inflow gust to the existing nonlinear CAA solver.